

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe Phase 3

Promoting inclusiveness in ESIWACE3 training and events

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

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Introduction

ESiWACE3 is committed to fostering engagement strategies that promote a more inclusive and diverse community. To support a welcoming and diverse community of Earth system modelling across Earth system sciences and high-performance computing, we are implementing activities to create a more equitable environment, focusing on addressing gender and geographical diversity.

Our events engage members of the HPC scientific community, technology providers, and users. We have adopted some guidelines to ensure they are as inclusive as possible. These are intended to help those planning, organising and running ESiWACE3 events to ensure that the events are open, welcoming and beneficial to all. Not all points in the following checklists will be relevant every time, but we hope that they will serve as reminders of the areas to think about at each stage of the planning and organisation process.

The following guidelines should not be considered as the final word but, instead, we will be glad to receive your feedback and continue to improve them in the light of your experiences.

Before the event

The planning stage

- Ensure that **the organising team is diverse** and includes people from under-represented groups. Discuss the need to avoid unconscious bias explicitly, and ensure that all voices are heard. Be prepared to address resistance by emphasising that gender balance and regional diversity do not compromise quality. Instead, they enhance discussions, introduce diverse perspectives, and often lead to fresh, innovative ideas.
- **Collaborate with existing initiatives** such as Women in High Performance Computing (WHPC) and other networks **to identify and connect with diverse presenters**. Using these resources helps ensure that the same few female/under-represented speakers are not repeatedly asked to contribute, avoiding an undue burden on them. Include diverse speakers throughout the core elements of the programme, ensuring they are integral to the event.
- Take **care when choosing dates** to avoid religious holidays and allow for a good work-life balance. For longer events, consider offering childcare options to make the event more accessible and family-friendly.
- Ensure that **all social events are inclusive**. Provide non-alcoholic drink options as a standard, along with food options that accommodate all dietary restrictions, preferences, and allergies. Sporting activities should be welcoming and accessible, with no gender segregation and with the option for participants to opt out without feeling excluded. Consider offering nearby quiet spaces for those who prefer a more relaxed environment or need a break from social activities.

Communication and registration

- **Publicise the event** through networks such as Women in HPC and not only through generalist channels.
- **Ensure that publicity material sets a welcoming tone.** Include an explicit statement in the event notification that applications from people in under-represented groups will be especially welcomed. Publicise a speaker list that demonstrates that participants from diverse backgrounds will find role models with whom they identify before they need to decide whether to apply. Make materials accessible for visual impairments and use culturally neutral language, colours and symbols to avoid unintended offence.
- As a condition of registration, require participants to **agree to accept a code of conduct** at the event. This sends the message to the less confident that the tone of the event will be supportive.
- Ask for **all relevant information at registration**: e.g. dietary needs, accessibility needs, etc. Again, this sends the message that the organisers are taking accessibility seriously. Offer the option for people registering to give their preferred name and pronouns, and ensure that these are respected: e.g. provide name badges that use the preferred name and pronouns.

Making the logistics accessible

- Ensure that **the venue is physically accessible** to all and that all the required facilities (such as toilets, child-care rooms, etc.) are close to hand. Remember that people's accessibility needs may not be visible, and they may not wish to disclose them.
- The **environment should be quiet**, and the sound system should ensure that presentations are audible to those hard of hearing and that they can participate freely in informal discussions.
- **Visual materials** should all be easily intelligible to those with colour vision deficiency.

During the event

Setting the tone

- Ensure the visible and active involvement of diverse speakers, instructors and helpers.
- Identify clearly whom participants should approach if they have any further needs. Ideally, this person should be focused primarily on accessibility and inclusivity, and have authority to provide accommodations and change conduct rules if needed.
- Consider adopting a set of social rules, such as those developed by the Recurse Center. (See Appendix 2.) Presenting these in the introduction to the event can help to illustrate the behaviours expected from all participants.

Encouraging participation by all

- Make available **multiple channels for participants to ask questions or seek help**. At least one of these might usefully be semi-anonymous. Not everyone feels comfortable speaking up in front of the whole group.
- In group discussions, consider **explicitly inviting and welcoming contributions** from quieter participants, but ensure that they do not feel under pressure to speak if they do not wish to.

Follow up

- Include explicit questions about inclusiveness in feedback questionnaires. For example: “To what extent did you feel welcome and supported during the event.” “What could we have done to improve accessibility?”
- Consider the extent to which the demographics of the event reflect ESIWACE’s diversity objectives. Record any learning points and pass them back to the WP5 and WP6 teams.

Contact details

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ESIWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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Appendix 1

Suggested text for inclusion in a registration form

Inclusivity and respect declaration:

We are committed to creating a welcoming and inclusive environment for all participants. We expect all attendees to treat each other with respect and kindness, regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, gender identity, sexual orientation, disability, religion or any other characteristic. Discrimination or harassment of any kind will not be tolerated. By registering to attend this event, you agree to uphold these values and to contribute to a positive and respectful atmosphere.

Include a tick box for respondents to accept the declaration.

(Adapted from text suggested by the European Institute for Gender Equality:

<https://eige.europa.eu/publications-resources/toolkits-guides/words-matter/communication-formats/events>)

Suggested social rules

Social rules developed by the Recurse Center (<https://www.recurse.com/social-rules#footnote-2>):

Social rules

RC has four social rules. They help create a friendly, intellectual environment where you can spend as much of your energy as possible on programming.

The social rules are:

- No well-actually's
- No feigned surprise
- No backseat driving
- No subtle -isms

The social rules name subtle behaviors that put other people down or show how much we know instead of supporting each other's learning. They work together with the [self-directives](#) to make RC an even better place to learn and grow.

For example, working at the edge of your abilities requires taking emotional risks, and the social rules help create an environment where it's safe to do that. Letting someone know that they impacted you by breaking a social rule and accepting that feedback gracefully when you're the one who messed up are important ways to learn generously. This allows everyone to keep working and growing together.

One thing that often surprises people about the social rules is that we expect people to break them from time to time. This means they're different from [our code of conduct](#), which covers behaviors that are never acceptable, like abuse, discrimination, and harassment.

No well-actually's

Alice: I just installed Linux on my computer!

Bob: It's actually called GNU/Linux.

A well-actually is when you correct someone about something that's not relevant to the conversation or tangential to what they're trying to say. They're bad because they aren't helpful, break the flow of conversation, and focus attention on the person making the well actually.

This rule can be a bit tricky because there isn't a clear line between relevant to the conversation and not. Sometimes your correction might actually be necessary, and it could still come off as annoying when you make it. The best rule of thumb is, if you're not sure whether something needs to be said right now, hold off and see

what happens. You can always say it later if it turns out there's no way for the conversation to move forward without your correction.

No feigning surprise

Dan: What's the command line?

Carol: Wait, you've never used the command line?

Feigned surprise is when you act surprised when someone doesn't know something. Responding with surprise in this situation makes people feel bad for not knowing things and less likely to ask questions in the future, which makes it harder for them to learn.

No feigning surprise isn't a great name. When someone acts surprised when you don't know something, it doesn't matter whether they're pretending to be surprised or actually surprised. The effect is the same: the next time you have a question, you're more likely to keep your mouth shut. An accurate name for this rule would be *no acting surprised when someone doesn't know something*, but it's a mouthful, and at this point, the current name has stuck.

No backseat driving

Bob: What's the name of the string copy function?

Alice: Strncpy.

Eve: (*from across the room*) You should use strncpy. It's safer.

Backseat driving is when you lob advice from across the room (or across the online chat) without really joining or engaging in a conversation. Because you haven't been participating in the conversation, it's easy to miss something important and give advice that's not actually helpful. Even if your advice is correct, it's rude to bust into a conversation without asking. If you overhear a conversation where you could be helpful, the best thing to do is to ask to join.

No subtle -isms

Carol: Windows is hard to use.

Bob: No way. Windows is so easy to use that even my mom can use it.

Subtle -isms are subtle expressions of racism, sexism, ageism, homophobia, transphobia and other kinds of bias and prejudice. They are small things that make others feel unwelcome, things that we all sometimes do by mistake. Subtle -isms make people feel like they don't belong at RC. We want to create an environment where everyone can focus all their energy on programming. It's hard to do that if you're regularly being made to wonder whether you belong.

Subtle -isms can also be things that you do instead of say. This includes things like boxing out the only woman at the whiteboard during a discussion or assuming someone isn't a programmer because of their race or gender.

The fourth social rule is more complicated than the others. Not everyone agrees on what constitutes a subtle -ism. Subtle -isms are baked into society in ways that can make them hard to recognize. And not everyone experiences subtle -isms in the same way: subtle homophobia won't hurt someone who's straight in the same way it hurts someone who's gay.

There's another part of *no subtle -isms*: If you see racism, sexism, etc. outside of RC, please don't bring it in. For example, please don't start a discussion about the latest offensive comment from Random Tech Person Y. Everyone who comes to RC should have the same opportunity to focus on programming, and people from oppressed groups often find discussions of racism, sexism, etc. particularly hard to tune out. There are many places to discuss and debate these issues, but there are few where people can avoid them. RC is one of those places.

How do they work?

The social rules are lightweight. You should not be afraid of breaking a social rule. These are things that everyone does, and breaking one doesn't make you a bad person. If someone says, "hey, you just feigned surprise," or "that's subtly sexist," don't worry. Just apologize, reflect for a second, and move on.

The social rules aren't for punishing people. They help make RC a pleasant environment where you are free to be yourself, tackle things outside your comfort zone, and focus on programming.